

Education & Skills

July 2025

The **Western Balkans Agenda on Innovation, Research, Education, Culture, Youth and Sport** is a long-term strategy from the EU and the Western Balkans (WB) for cooperation with the region. It will contribute to the region’s economic and societal development and builds on three main pillars: Political, Thematic, and Regional.

The project POLICY ANSWERS monitors the implementation of the Western Balkans Agenda, and the broader context, progress and achievements are summarised in regular reports. In this Monitoring Card, you find the results of the third round of data collection during 2024 and the first months of 2025 in comparison to the data collected in the previous second monitoring round.

In terms of Education & Skills, the monitoring focuses on the context indicator “Academic Freedom Index” and various achievements outlined in the WB Agenda (see next page).

Achievements in a wider context of the Western Balkans Agenda

Source
Academic Freedom Index <https://academic-freedom-index.net/> (accessed 1 July 2025)

* This designation is without prejudice to positions on status, and is in line with UNSCR 1244/1999 and the ICJ Opinion on the Kosovo declaration of independence.

Regional Indicators

Western Balkans Steering Platform meetings on Education and Training		
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Western Balkans Economy Indicators

Indicator and overall assessment of the region	Integration & stronger participation in EU programmes and initiatives				Fostered capacity building for R&I, education and Vocational Education and Training (VET)	
	Supporting the implementation of the EU acquis					
Albania	No Twinning projects & TAIEX missions					
Bosnia and Herzegovina	No Twinning projects & TAIEX missions					
Kosovo	No Twinning projects & TAIEX missions					
Montenegro	No Twinning projects & TAIEX missions					
North Macedonia	No Twinning projects & TAIEX missions					
Serbia	No Twinning projects & TAIEX missions					

Legend: Information not available

Highlights

Agreement on Access to Higher Education and Admission to Study in the Western Balkans signed by the Western Balkans leaders at the 10th Berlin Process Summit
Increasing Western Balkans interconnectedness and mobility-driven R&I by successfully piloting the POLICY ANSWERS Western Balkans Mobility Scheme

